

A FACTOR ANALYSIS OF CLIMATE VULNERABILITY AND ADAPTIVE LIVELIHOODS CHUDANGA DISTRICT BANGLADESH

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Abstract: This study examines the multidimensional structure of household vulnerability and adaptation using factor analysis. Due to the analysis, the data was collected by a face-to-face questionnaire survey in 300 rural households in Chuadanga district, Bangladesh. The analysis identifies five key essential dimensions: climate shocks with institutional support, agricultural adaptation constraints, demographic pressure, financial stress with credit reliance, and human and land capital. The findings show that household vulnerability is shaped by a combination of environmental exposure, limited adaptation capacity, population pressure, financial insecurity, and unequal access to resources. These interconnected factors explain differences in how households experience and respond to climate-related risks. The study suggests that improving resilience requires integrated strategies that address both environmental challenges and socio-economic conditions.

Keywords: Climate vulnerability, Factor analysis, Agricultural adaptation, Household resilience, Livelihoods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change has become one of the most serious challenges for rural livelihoods, especially in developing countries like Bangladesh [1]. Increasing temperature, irregular rainfall, frequent droughts, and extreme weather events are directly affecting agriculture, income stability, and food security [2]. Rural households, which largely depend on agriculture and natural resources, are among the most vulnerable groups [3]. This study uses factor analysis to understand the key factors that shape household vulnerability and adaptation. It aims to identify the underlying dimensions that explain how households experience and respond to climate shocks.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO shows data suitability for factor analysis (acceptable if >0.6). Bartlett's test checks correlation, and $p < 0.05$ means factor analysis is appropriate [4].

B. Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is an unsupervised machine learning technique used to identify underlying latent factors that explain the relationships among observed variables [5].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

KMO and Bartlett's tests: KMO and Bartlett's tests confirmed that the data were suitable for factor analysis, with adequate sampling adequacy (KMO = 0.651) and significant correlations among variables (Bartlett's test, $p = 0.00$). The retained factors collectively captured the major dimensions of variation in the dataset.

Table 1 presents five main factors of household vulnerability and adaptation in the study area: Climate Shock and Institutional Relief Index, Agricultural Adaptation Deficit, Demographic Burden and Non-Migration Index, Financial Distress and Credit Reliance, and Human and Land Capital Profile. Vulnerability is shaped by climate exposure, limited adaptation capacity, demographic pressure, financial stress, and differences in access to human and land resources.

Table 1. Factor Analysis Results

Factor	Variables
Climate Shock and Institutional Relief	Income loss, extreme weather exposure, drought relief, extension access, climate training, and asset quality.
Agricultural Adaptation Deficit	Seasonal drought, housing type, land ownership, river irrigation, and drought-tolerant crops.
Demographic Burden and Non-Migration	Dependency ratio, household size, age of head, and migration status.
Financial Distress and Credit Reliance	Drought losses, loan/credit access
Human and Land Capital	Years of schooling, cultivable land area, agriculture as the main occupation, and age of head.

Therefore, a five-factor solution was retained as the most parsimonious and interpretable representation of the underlying data structure. The five factors explained 35.18%, 22.41%, 14.01%, 17.32%, and 10.08% of the total variance, respectively. Together, these factors accounted for 99.00% of the overall variance in the dataset, indicating that they captured nearly all of the major dimensions of variation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study shows that household vulnerability is affected by several related factors. Climate shocks, such as droughts and extreme weather, increase vulnerability, especially when support

Figure 1: Scree Plot

The scree plot (Figure 1) was used to determine the number of factors to retain. The eigenvalues decreased sharply from the first to the fifth factor and then leveled off. A clear elbow was observed at the fifth factor, indicating that five factors are sufficient to explain most of the variation in the data. Therefore, five factors were retained for further analysis.

services are weak. Poor farming conditions, including limited irrigation, modern technology, and agricultural support, make it harder for households to adapt. Large family size and more dependents also put pressure on household resources. Financial problems, such as low income, loss of assets, and reliance on loans, reduce households' ability to cope with difficulties. In addition, differences in land ownership, education, and access to resources lead to unequal levels of resilience. These findings suggest that reducing vulnerability requires better climate support, improved farming systems, greater financial assistance, and improved access to education and resources.

References

- [1] K. M. Parvez and R. Hasan, "Spatial land transformation and the psychosocial exposure of climate migrants in southwestern Bangladesh," *Geopsychiatry*, vol. xx, p. 100065, 2026.
- [2] S. Mahmood, R. Iqbal, S. Ilyas, E. Zaka, I. Fayyaz, and K. Haroon, "Climate change induced extreme weather events and food security," *Spectrum of Engineering Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 488–511, 2026.
- [3] A. Kumar and T. Mohanasundari, "Assessment of livelihood vulnerability to climate change among tribal communities in Chhindwara and Dhar district, Central India," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 8843, 2025.
- [4] N. Yusoff, N. H. Saad, B. Abdullah, M. H. M. Rusli, and S. Muhamud-Kayat, "Exploratory factor analysis of an emergency remote teaching and learning survey for tertiary level using SPSS," *Asian Journal of University Education*, vol. 21, no. 3, 2025.
- [5] I. Moustaki, F. Steele, Y. Chen, and D. Bartholomew, *Analysis of Multivariate Social Science Data: Statistical Machine Learning Methods*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2026.